

OneGeochemistry (1GC) Governance

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1 Executive Summary

1.1 Scope

OneGeochemistry (1GC) is international and diverse in background, encompassing such fields as high and low-temperature geochemistry, petrology, meteoritics, fluid-rock interaction, isotope geochemistry, and organic geochemistry (definition adapted from the Geochemical Society).

1.2 Vision and Mission

OneGeochemistry (1GC) is a global initiative that brings together major geochemical data providers and the geochemical research community with the objective of establishing global standards and best practices for FAIR geochemical laboratory analytical data that are as open as possible and as closed as necessary. 1GC operates as a [CODATA Working Group](#).

Vision: OneGeochemistry is working towards an interoperable global geochemical data network that links international geochemical data service providers.

Mission: Advance scientific knowledge and discovery by promoting best practices and protocols for reporting geochemical data that will make the data not only globally findable and accessible, but also interoperable and reusable (FAIR).

1.3 Overall Structure & Definitions of Governing Bodies

1.3.1 Steering Committee (SC):

The 1GC SC works towards realising the above stated vision and mission, i.e., to create an interoperable global geochemical data network.

1.3.2 Advisory Board (AB):

The 1GC AB provides advice, feedback and recommendations on and for the 1GC strategy and priority program areas. The AB is constituted by representatives of geochemical societies and associations that represent the geo- and cosmochemical community at large.

1.3.3 Expert Committees:

Review, develop and update standards to enable FAIR and Open Geochemistry as the foundational elements of the 1GC data network. Standards will be registered with the CGI (Commission for the Management and Application of Geoscience Information) of the IUGS (International Union of Geological Sciences), published, and advertised on the 1GC website and in the IUPAC (International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry) brown book. Committees are encouraged to create citable publications in the peer-reviewed geochemical literature.

a. Scientific expert committees (SECs):

- Develop & maintain scientific content standards (i.e. vocabularies & best practice recommendations).

b. Technical expert committee (TEC):

- Develop & maintain technical standards;
- Implement scientific content standards for CGI registry; and
- Develop technical standards required for a global geochemistry data network.

Community Engagement Committee (CEC):

Spreads the 1GC vision and mission statements on various levels of abstractions, from the simple vision to technical details. Prepares promotional / educational material and leads outreach to create new scientific expert committees.

1.3 Definition of Standards

A standard is defined by the CODATA RDM Terminologies (2024) as a “*set of agreed-upon and documented guidelines, specifications, accepted practices, technical requirements, or terminologies that have been prepared by a standards developing organization or group, and published in accordance with established procedures*”. 1GC distinguishes between best practices, scientific content standards, and technical standards as follows:

- Best practices:** description of workflows and QA/QC procedures recommended for a particular data type by a particular community.
- Scientific content standard:** standard defining vocabularies/terminologies, minimum variables and formats for reporting and describing individual geochemical data types.

- c. **Technical standard:** discipline-agnostic standard that defines file formats, computational frameworks, communication protocols, persistent identifiers to enable data sharing and reuse. Here we specifically refer to the technical implementations of scientific content standards, such as machine-actionable structured vocabularies.

For approval by 1GC, best practices and standards are expected to be agreed by a global community and to align with FAIR and CARE principles.

2 Membership

2.1 Types of Memberships

1GC defines its membership as the following 3 types:

Type 1 - General Members: Individuals, groups, organisations, applied service providers such as publishers, instrument manufacturers, with geo- or cosmochemical goals, or specific technical/digital expertise from the research, government, industry or private sectors.

Type 2 - Data Systems: Repository and database providers, research and government infrastructures that develop and/or operate substantial, publicly and long-term available geochemical data services.

Type 3 - Societies/Associations: Professional societies/associations with goals related to geo- or cosmochemical research.

In addition to formal membership, 1GC invites contribution to its goals by *Sponsors* via financial or in-kind contribution of resources.

2.2 Membership Terms

Members are expected to align with and support the goals, interests, and principles of the 1GC initiative. This implies agreement to the following terms:

- a. All 1GC members are expected to contribute to the development and/or promotion of best practices and standards for laboratory analytical data to the best of their ability and knowledge.
- b. Type 2 members are expected, to the best of their ability, to commit to implementing best practices and standards for laboratory analytical data as recommended or endorsed by 1GC, such as core (metadata) schema of common minimum variables and vocabularies.
- c. Type 2 members are expected to collaborate on making data systems more complementary and on minimising, to the degree possible, duplication of data holdings and services.

Membership provides different benefits and responsibilities for each type:

- a. Type 1 Member Terms: Participation in, and initiation of, expert committees and other working groups; information via email list / newsletter; nomination of representatives to the Steering Committee and the Advisory Board.
- b. Type 2 Member Terms: Each member nominates one representative to be a part of the Steering Committee.
- c. Type 3 Member Terms: Each member nominates a representative to the Advisory Board.

2.3 Membership Application

Membership is voluntary.

- Type 1 membership may be obtained through self-nomination via the 1GC website.
- Type 2 membership (data systems) requires a short application submitted to the 1GC contact email address. The 1GC Steering Committee (SC) reviews and approves membership applications on a monthly schedule.
- For Type 3 membership, including formal endorsement of 1GC and representation in the Advisory Board, societies/associations should liaise with the SC.

2.4 Termination of Membership

A member may be excluded from OneGeochemistry by resolution of the Steering Committee if it negligently or deliberately damages the interests of 1GC in a gross manner, specifically by not complying with the membership terms described above.

Before passing its resolution, the reasons for the resolution passed by the Steering Committee shall be stated in writing and sent to the member concerned. A type 2 member may appeal against the resolution. The appeal shall be submitted to the Steering Committee within one month following receipt of the resolution. Within one month after the appeal has been filed in accordance with the applicable deadline, the Steering Committee shall convene a meeting with the Advisory Board to take the final decision on the exclusion of the member.

3 1GC Annual Assemblies

1GC holds an annual General Assembly in a virtual format to report on its progress, discusses current issues, and conducts elections. These meetings are public and will be rotated on time zones. These meetings will be recorded and recordings made available to all members.

In addition, an annual in-person meeting will be held as a Town Hall or equivalent at the annual Goldschmidt conference.

4 Committee Positions and Responsibilities

4.1 Steering Committee (SC)

4.1.1 Members & Roles

- a. Members of the 1GC SC represent the data systems and research data infrastructures of the 1GC network. Each participant data system may nominate one representative to the SC.
- b. The SC shall also include one representative of the 1GC Community Engagement Committee (also representing the Scientific Expert Committee(s)) and one representative from the Technical Expert Committee.
- c. The SC can appoint additional members through super (2/3) majority vote, representing active and skilled individuals from the data or geochemical community who actively help advance the goals of 1GC.
- d. If membership exceeds 15 persons, an executive (sub-)committee should be appointed.
- e. The SC is empowered to extend invitations to observers for participation in its meetings or those of its sub-committees.
- f. One member is elected by the SC members as chair and one as co-chair for the term of 2 years.
- g. Chair and co-chair are responsible for managing the day-to-day operation of 1GC. In that function, they prepare the meetings of the SC and the General Assembly (i.e. set and advertise meeting agendas), respond to enquiries, prepare the strategy and implementation plan, and implement all decisions taken.

4.1.2 Responsibilities

- a. The SC develops the strategy and implementation plans for achieving a global geochemical network, following advice from the Advisory Board.
- b. The SC determines the operational structures necessary to deliver an interoperable global geochemical network including:
 - i. Recommend implementation of content standards based on existing technical standards; and
 - ii. Identify technical developments required for setting up a framework for connecting nodes into a global federated network.
- c. The SC approves the Terms of Reference for any working groups or committees it deems necessary to establish and will formally approve their chairs.
- d. The SC defines and reviews criteria for 1GC membership, and approves applications for type 2 membership.

- e. The SC is responsible for maintaining the financial viability of 1GC and is authorised to establish membership fees and to seek other sources of funding in support.
- f. The SC shall convene a minimum of four times annually, or as deemed necessary. In addition, the annual in-person meeting shall be used to define the priority programme areas and implementation plan for the following year.
- g. An Annual Progress Report is to be published in the 1GC Zenodo community or an equivalent open platform for review by the Advisory Board, after which it will be advertised on the 1GC website.
- h. The SC shall report to the Advisory Board (AB) on the results and progress of the 1GC goals at the AB's annual meeting.

4.2 Advisory Board (AB)

4.2.1 Members & Roles

- a. Each society/association that endorses 1GC is encouraged to appoint one representative to join the 1GC AB.
- b. The SC nominates one of its members as an ex-officio member of the Advisory Board
- c. Additional members may be appointed by the SC to represent, for example:
 - i. Broader interested parties such as instrument manufacturers, exploration industry, publishers, funding agencies;
 - ii. Technical Standards Advice (e.g. representative from CODATA);
 - iii. A spokesperson from the Community Engagement Committee.

4.2.2 Responsibilities

- a. Establish in its first year the scope of the 1GC AB and determine how it will contribute to the 1GC mission. Suggested responsibilities of the 1GC AB may be
 - i. To advise the SC on the OneGeochemistry strategy including partnerships and funding opportunities and to help define priority programme areas; and
 - ii. To evaluate and provide feedback on the progress of the 1GC goals and make recommendations where/when necessary.

4.3 Expert Committees

Scientific Expert Committee (SEC)

4.3.1 Members & Roles

- a. Initiated by the SC or the broader 1GC membership based on need; members are appointed by the SC; community-led applications and self-nominations are encouraged.
- b. A SEC requires a minimum of 5 members with diverse membership (nationality, geography, career stage/role, gender, etc.).

- c. Membership of SECs should include at least one technical adviser to help guide the process of producing standards.
- d. A SEC elects one of their members as chair to lead the group and act as liaison to the SC.

4.3.2 Responsibilities

- a. Scientific expert committees develop scientific terms and content standards (conceptual or logical models).
- b. The chair of each committee reports to the SC at regular intervals (at least quarterly).

Technical Expert Committee (TEC)

4.3.3 Members & Roles

- a. Appointed by SC on permanent basis; community-led applications and nominations by Data System members encouraged.
- b. A TEC elects one of their members as chair to lead the group and act as liaison to the SC.

4.3.4 Responsibilities

- a. Review scientific standards proposed by SECs for feasibility.
- b. Develop technical implementations for scientific standards.
- c. Build cross-walks and/or mapping tools for parallel/similar vocabularies or metadata schemas.

4.4 Community Engagement Committee (CEC)

4.4.1 Members & Roles

- a. Members appointed by the SC; community-led applications and nominations by type 2 members encouraged.

4.4.2 Responsibilities

- a. Maintain the 1GC website.
- b. Develop promotional and educational content for the 1GC website, conferences and other outreach activities to be approved by SC to ensure consistency of messaging.
- c. Monitor potential conferences, workshops, etc and advise potential participation.
- d. Provide feedback from the community at large to the SC.

5 Notes

These bylaws may be changed following a super ($\frac{2}{3}$) majority vote of the SC, and after consultation with the AB.

A maximum of 3 consecutive re-appointments is recommended for chairs and co-chairs of any committee.